

SPECIFIC PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF CHILDREN'S LYMPHOCYTIC LEUKEMIA

Z. Sh. Salaeva

(Urganch Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy)

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Enter. Children's lymphocytic leukemia is pathomorphologically manifested by focal leukemic infiltration in the bone marrow and almost all lymphoid organs at the beginning of the disease. Lymphocytic leukemia is characterized by the appearance of leukemic infiltration in specific areas of lymphoid organs, depending on whether it develops from T or V lymphocytes. In lymphocytic leukemia, pathomorphological changes first appear in the stroma-vascular structures of organs, and then spread to the parenchyma.

Purpose of work. Characteristic pathomorphological changes of young children's lymphocytic leukemia were identified.

Inspection results. In the trepanobiopsy material, i.e. bone marrow, it was found that depending on the level of development of leukemia, in the case of a mild form, leukemic blast cells were collected in a focal form, and in a severe form, they occupied almost the entire area of the bone marrow and were diffusely infiltrated. Hemorrhagic foci, necrosis, hypoplasia of other bone marrow cells are often detected.

In children's lymphocytic leukemia, it can be noted that pathomorphologically specific symptoms are present in the thymus, spleen, lymph nodes and even the liver, starting from the bone marrow. In bone marrow, the disease is manifested by focal leukemic infiltration in most cases and differs from other types of leukemia by this sign. In the thymus, the information is clear, that is, mainly in T lymphocytic leukemia, the leukemic infiltration starts from the interstitial tissue of the thymus, then spreads to the parenchyma, and often the leukemic infiltration overwhelms the cortical layer.

Specific pathomorphological changes in the spleen are that, depending on the type of lymphocytic leukemia, in T lymphocytic leukemia mainly the marginal area and periarterial area undergo leukemic infiltration, while in V lymphocytic leukemia, the change begins in the marginal area and then completely occupies the lymphoid follicles.

Conclusion: 1. Children's lymphocytic leukemia is pathomorphologically manifested by leukemic infiltration of the bone marrow and almost all lymphoid organs in the beginning of the disease.

2. Lymphocytic leukemia is characterized by the appearance of leukemic infiltration in specific areas of lymphoid organs, depending on whether it develops from T or V lymphocytes.

